

Faith, Doubt and the Ocean: Analysing Yann Martel's Life of Pi

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the intricate interplay of faith, doubt and the ocean in Yann Martel's *Life of Pi*, exploring how these three elements influence each other resulting in the transformation of the titular character's faith. It aims to establish the evolving nature of Pi's faith, highlighting the importance of the ocean as the catalyst for doubt, addressing the ways in which adversities reshape understanding, and also emphasise the power of choice. An interpretative and textual approach is used to study *Life of Pi*, focusing on the themes and characters, to understand the impact of Pi's experiences in the ocean, and its connection to the evolution of his faith, evoked by doubt. The analysis essentially reveals Pi as a true believer, who, instead of giving up on his faith after his gruesome experiences, continues to uphold it with greater understanding. It also explains how it is the idea of the "better story" that *truly* marks the positive transformation Pi had undergone. This interpretation offers a fresh perspective on how Pi's faith was not one-dimensional, emphasising its growth, while acknowledging the role of the ocean and doubt in his story. It highlights how Martel masterfully redefines the experiences with crisis of faith, incorporating the brutality of nature, as he suggests that often the most difficult solutions are found from within.

KEY WORDS: Faith, Religion, Doubt, Ocean, Transformation

INTRODUCTION

A philosophical novel is a genre of literature that blends compelling narratives with philosophical concepts, often delving into questions about morality, human nature, and even religion. It first gained momentum in the 18th century with the influence of the Enlightenment, which was characterised by reason and social reform. It is still a very relevant genre in today's world, offering distinct perspectives and allows us to explore the human and societal conditions, despite some criticism over its sometimes overly didactic nature, and the ever-shifting literary preferences. Popular philosophical novels include Daniel Defoe's *Robinson Crusoe*, and Albert Camus' *The Stranger*.

Yann Martel is a Canadian author, who in 2001, published his magnum opus, “Life of Pi”, an international best-seller, which won him the prestigious Man Booker Prize the following year. In this critically acclaimed philosophical novel, centered on an Indian boy lost in the Pacific Ocean, in a life boat with a Royal Bengal Tiger, Martel uses magic-realism to intricately weave a story about survival, faith, and the nature of storytelling. Studies have extensively explored the themes of faith, religion and human nature, and its post-modern narrative structure.

While scholars like James Mensch highlight the themes of human nature as he argues that, “*Martel’s tale is an account of alterity—the alterity of both animals and God. Like Pi, we tend to define our humanity by drawing a line between it and our animality, where the human is defined by a boundary excluding the animal.*” (Mensch, 2), others such as James Wood question the plausibility and depth of the story. Wood points out in his review titled ‘Credulity’, “*Martel certainly ensures that his tale feels real, but there is a sense in which Pi does not. And so we tend to credit the plausibility of the story rather than believing its reality. The absence of real religious discussion during the survival story is all the more odd given the novel’s coda, which is explicitly about faith and belief.*”

Therefore, in this paper it is argued that the titular character, Pi, *has* experienced a transformation in his faith, during his days as a castaway in the Pacific, evoked by doubt. Ultimately, this paper establishes the ocean as a source of divine intervention, which though magnificent, brought hardships and doubt, urging Pi to see beyond, and deepen his faith. To establish this argument, this paper will analyse Pi's journey of faith, from before his castaway days, and through his days in the Pacific, exploring how his faith evolves through the adversities, and how the ocean, by kindling doubt in him, sets the stage for this evolution, finally culminating in Pi choosing the “better story,” as it establishes the birth of a renewed doubt-integrated faith.

I. PI’S PRE-OCEAN FAITH AND ITS FOUNDATION

Piscine Molitor Patel, or simply, Pi, was an Indian boy, born to a Hindu family in Pondicherry, Tamil Nadu. And, unlike his family who did not value religion as such, Pi was *genuinely* religious. Pi believed that we are born without a religion until someone introduces us to God. And for him, it was his Aunt Rohini, who took him to a temple when he was a baby. Though he had no explicit memory of that first time, he says, “*A germ of religious exaltation, no bigger than a mustard seed, was sown in me and left to germinate.*” (Martel, 47) This religious rapture has been growing and thriving in him since then, fueled by the stories of the mighty Gods, with every little detail of the Hindu religious tradition signifying faith, and through it he notices an

ounce of divinity in everything. He says about Hinduism, “*With its notions in mind I see my place in the universe.*” (Martel, 49)

At fourteen, he adopted Christianity, when he went to a church, during a family vacation at Munnar. Despite attending a Christian school, he had never entered a church, and knew even less about the religion. At the church, he was warmly received by Father Martin, who told him the story of Christ. Pi was rather confused at the fact that there was this “God” who was *punished* for humanity’s sins, who *starved*, was *crucified*, and experienced *death*, everything that contradicted the Hindu Gods, who were “*With shine and power and might. Such as can rescue and save and put down evil.*” (Martel, 55) The flawed nature of Christ bothered him, but during every meeting with Father Martin, all his bewildered questions were answered with one single word, “Love”. So, as he accepted this simple truth, learnt and understood more and more about him, Pi was deeply moved by the very nature of Christ that he could not accept, *his humanity*.

The very next year, at fifteen, he adopted Islam. It was a Muslim bread-maker, Satish Kumar, who introduced the religion to Pi, who he befriended after stumbling upon the man at the small shop he owned. It was the story of the Beloved, the connectivity between the God and the devotees, and the religion’s beautiful and simple practices that moved him and drew him in. He went to the mosque with Satish, prayed together with the other devotees, participated in the rituals and chanting of the Qur’an, finding peace in the *very* involved nature of the religion. He says, “*It felt good to bring my forehead to the ground. Immediately it felt like a deeply religious contact.*” (Martel, 61)

In this manner, Pi came to adopt a multi-religious faith, as he embraced the core of each religion—the *energy* in Hinduism, the *humanity* in Christianity, and the *simplicity* in Islam. But, his faith was innocent, unmarred by grief or doubt troubling his heart, as he himself says, “*I just want to love God.*” (Martel, 69) Until the time he was sixteen, before the tragic shipwreck that completely disrupted the peaceful tides of his life, Pi’s involvement with religious faith was for the comfort, the ritualistic continuity it provided. Until then, he could easily dismiss any doubts about God’s purpose, and was innocently afraid of anything that challenged religion. Like once when his Biology teacher, who was an atheist, deemed religion to be “darkness”, and questioned the presence of God, Pi, who couldn’t say anything, confessed, “*I was more afraid that in a few words thrown out he might destroy something that I loved. What if his words had the effect of polio on me? What a terrible disease that must be if it could kill God in a man.*” (Martel, 28)

And so, until the fateful night of the shipwreck that left him orphaned in the great Pacific Ocean, Pi did not know of desperation, helplessness, and *such* grief that chokes you, something that forces man to truly question the presence and purpose of the merciful God.

II. THE OCEAN AS A CATALYST FOR DOUBT, AND THE CRISIS OF FAITH

When Pi set out for Canada with his family and some of their zoo animals, a journey forced by India's changing government, he had not expected to lose everything that he loved, and end up orphaned in the middle of the Pacific. But then, the *Tsimtsum*, the Japanese cargo ship that was supposed to carry them safely to Canada, sunk, and Pi found himself to be the sole survivor of a devastating shipwreck, in a life boat, with the company of an injured zebra, a hyena, an orangutan called Orange Juice, and Richard Parker, the tiger.

Pi had lost everything in a matter of *minutes*. The tragedy was real, and the trauma immediate. Because, here was this *boy*, no older than sixteen, stranded all alone in the middle of a vast, lonely ocean, with no sign of rescue or any sort of comfort. In the first few days, Pi had hoped that in response to the distress calls that might have been sent by the ship, rescue teams would arrive and he would be saved. He even imagined his family to be already rescued and that they would be waiting for him in Canada. But none of that happened, as he sadly said, "*Clouds that gathered where the ships were supposed to appear, and the passing of the day, slowly did the job of unbending my smile.*" (Martel, 123) There was also the animalistic savagery that he had to witness, as the animals attacked, killed, and ate at each other, finally leaving him alone with Richard Parker. These scenes of utmost brutality also had a role in scarring Pi. He confesses, "*My thoughts swung wildly. I was either fixed on practical details of immediate survival or transfixed by pain, weeping silently, my mouth open and my hands at my head.*" (Martel, 111) In the midst of desperately clinging to life, Pi was even unable to properly grieve the loss of his family; he could not *afford* to.

Pi had gone without water or food, the first few days. And even after finding the treasure chest of a supply box, he had to consciously monitor his intake of his nourishments. From catching rainwater, and purifying the saline ocean water for fresh water, to hunting from the ocean for food, and building his tools and accommodations, Pi was head-deep in trying to keep himself alive. There was also the constant threat, yet comforting presence of Richard Parker, whom he had to control, share the lifeboat with, and *provide* to ensure its life also. Nature also played its fair share, making sure that Pi was constantly in a state of desperation and misery, as it either tossed the lifeboat around during a storm, or brought little to no food Pi's way.

The ocean is a symbol of the *unknown*, and mirrors Pi's own internal journey. Here, it was also a witness to everything Pi had suffered. The ocean was something of a force that he had to confront throughout his days as a castaway. It was as if the ocean was challenging Pi, as it hurled difficulties at him constantly. It is true that the ocean was the source of the majority of

providence for Pi, but its vast and unpredictable nature was a major threat to him as well. But throughout his ordeal, Pi tried his best to keep his faith alive, something that gave him a sense of comfort and safety. He constantly calls God for his rescue, considering food and the rain that brings freshwater to be God's gift, and expressing his gratitude. He even had prayer timings for everyday. In this way, Pi tried to see divine mercy in every little solace he received. It was almost ravenous and desperate at times, the way he tried to associate everything with God, trying his best to not lose God in himself. But he confesses how it was difficult to cling to that faith at times. There were moments when doubt would worm its way under his skin, and eat away at his faith and hope.

Pi was thus, for the first time in his life, forced to question God's existence and his sense of justice, after the shipwreck and throughout his days as a castaway. The magnificent, yet ruthless ocean led him to a point of spiritual crisis that Pi was unprepared for, something that *could've* killed him from the inside. But, here's when the idea of the "better story" comes; Pi's act of choosing this *story*, showcasing how he embraced his doubts rather than succumbing to them.

III. THE OCEAN AS A SOURCE OF TRANSCENDENCE, AND RENEWED FAITH

Though the ocean was a witness to, and also inflicted much of Pi's suffering, it had also offered Pi magical and awe-inspiring moments. The picturesque sunrises and sunsets, the bioluminescent jellyfishes, the starry nights, every one of these moments had indeed given him a much needed respite. But, the ocean was an unknown territory, completely unpredictable. And, given the idea of God's omnipresence, the ocean itself may even be considered *as* God, putting Pi through a divine test, pushing the limits of his faith, while also granting him little comforts that kept his hope alive. In that sense, Pi's survival had in itself been a very spiritual act. The sheer act of survival, as he pushed himself to his limits, showcases his *stubborn* will to live which was always guided by his faith, even when doubt seemed to settle into his very bones.

After the harrowing 227 days in the Pacific, Pi finally reaches land, Mexico to be exact; Richard Parker escapes into the woods nearby the shore immediately. There, at the hospital, hearing the news about the sole survivor of the Tsimtsum shipwreck, two Japanese officers from the Maritime Department, arrived to get possible information about the shipwreck. But what they got from Pi for information, was a *bizarre* story of him in a lifeboat with a bunch of animals.

It was indeed an impossibility that a human could survive, travel for such a long period no less, along with an apex predator. The officers thought Pi was making a fool out of them, and asked him to tell them what *actually* happened. And that is how Pi narrates another story, replacing the

animals with humans. In this story, the zebra was the sailor, the hyena was the cook, Orange Juice was his own mother, and Richard Parker was himself. But, in this version, when the officers heard of the brutal cannibalism exhibited by the humans, replaced by the animals killing each other (which was normal to their *nature*), they deemed the one with the animals to be the “better story.” In response, Pi says, “*Thank you. And so it goes with God.*” (Martel, 317) Actually, this cryptic response hints that the reality of what actually happened after the shipwreck was indeed what Pi narrated as the second story, and that Pi himself chose to believe the “better story.” Because, well, in dire circumstances, humans are indeed capable of extreme brutality to ensure their lives.

Earlier in the beginning, Pi had once confessed that he feels a kinship with atheists, unlike with agnostics. Because, atheists have a strong faith or belief in the absence of God, like the ones who are religious have a strong faith in the existence of God. But, agnostics on the other hand, were *doubtful* about the presence of God. Pi considers having doubts to be useful for a while, but then we ought to move on. So, he says regarding agnostics, “*To choose doubt as a philosophy of life is akin to choosing immobility as a means of transportation.*” (Martel, 28)

Now, when you look at it, the reason behind Pi’s choice of the “better story” is ultimately to protect and save himself from becoming an agnostic himself. After his days as a castaway, during his period of recovery in the small coastal village in Mexico, Pi likely had a breakdown, when he truly questioned the existence of God and the entire point of his faith. He likely had questioned why a merciful God would let his devout follower suffer in such a cruel way. And so, when the depth of what had actually happened during those 227 days as a castaway—the reality of his own animalistic behaviour sunk in—Pi must have realised how he had been lost, and that there was no humanity in what actually transpired. There was no presence of *God*. This knowledge had definitely put Pi into unimaginable terror and misery. And thus, to protect himself from any more mental harm, Pi creates the “better story,” consciously choosing to accept it as his reality. This story, which had mercy and was much more humane, helped Pi forget the way his mother was viciously killed in front of his eyes, and also bury away his own savagery.

Thus, it was indeed Pi’s defense mechanism that led to the creation of the “better story.” Pi chose to keep his faith alive to protect himself, but at the same time, he has learnt to acknowledge the doubts. It was the only way he could have had the willpower to build back everything he had lost. And at long last, his loss, the utmost grief and helplessness, the brutal struggle for survival, everything, when you look at the bigger picture, can be considered as a part of God’s greater plan, that ultimately lead to the transformation of Pi’s faith, with the ocean, by all means, being the source of this divine intervention.

CONCLUSION

Faith is a deeply resonating virtue, which, by connecting us to a higher power, provides us with hope. Conversely, doubt, questions the presence of this higher power, their purpose, and challenges our faith in them. Yet, doubt can be viewed as a catalyst for strengthening one's faith, an integral part of the journey in attaining a deeper faith. And the very core of Yann Martel's *Life of Pi* resonates with this idea, with it being "*a story that will make you believe in God.*" (Martel, XII)

In this paper it is argued that the titular character of the story, Pi, with the beautiful, yet ruthless ocean being the cause of transcendence and the catalyst for doubt, has experienced a profound transformation in his faith. Pi's multi-religious faith, which was initially characterised by his curiosity and pure "love" for God, matured and evolved after losing everything he'd once loved in the shipwreck. The vast ocean played the part of the perfect setting for this radical change, while also being the cause of the majority of his suffering, challenging Pi *relentlessly* as he tried his hardest to keep both his faith and hope alive. And finally, when the doubt induced by the ocean, and the reality of what had *actually* transpired during his castaway days threatened to tear him apart, Pi creates the "better story." It is the creation of this story and Pi's conscious choice to believe it, that highlights the transformation that Pi's faith had undergone, as he, instead of succumbing to the bitter doubts, learnt to embrace them.

Through this paper's analysis of *Life of Pi*, it is established that Pi's creation of the "better story", has its roots from the fact that he was unwilling to live an immobilising life of an agnostic. It can also be acknowledged that Pi is a *true* believer, who did not let the pain that he suffered to *kill* "God" in him. And according to Pi's way of looking at things, it can be said that the entire harrowing experience was a part of God's greater plan, who, with the help of the ocean, or even *as* the ocean, taught Pi a lesson in faith and doubt, which culminated in the evolution of his faith.

Ultimately, Yann Martel's *Life of Pi* is a story of survival, not only about protecting and preserving the physical body through intense ordeal, but also the mind and soul. It is a story that serves as a reminder to have faith in what we believe, but at the same time, to acknowledge the doubts and fears that come along with it. Because, there is no one without the other. And also, it is a story that reminds us that in the end, everything is a matter of choice, and we *do* have a choice in everything. It all depends on what we choose as our "better story", even when it feels like we are drowning in an ocean of doubts.

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